

Kruskal's algorithm for solving the both balanced unbalanced acceptable and prohibited route transportation problems

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Abstract: A Transportation Problem (TP) involves figuring out how to effectively use the resources of “m” supply stations to meet the needs of “n” demand places while also maximizing efficiency. In general, a variable cost of delivering the goods from one supply location to a demand point or a similar limitation should be taken into consideration while trying to discover the optimum solution. Products are manufactured by businesses at sources, which are then shipped to customers at destinations. Each supplier may only transport a certain amount of the goods, and each client destination must receive the minimum amount. Direct shipments from a source to a destination are the only feasible ones. In general, "Classical Transportation Problems (CTP)" are problems with the aforementioned criteria. These problems are due to the transportation of a homogenous good from several supply sites to various demand locations. Prohibited Route Transportation Problem (PRTP) is a special type of TP. Transporting things from one location to another may not be practicable if circumstances like traffic laws, hazardous conditions on the road, etc. occur. Assigning an extremely high cost, such as M (or ∞), to such a route can be used to address such circumstances. This paper proposed an alternative algorithm to resolve both CTP and PRTP using Kruskal's algorithm. Kruskal's algorithm is a technique to find the Minimum Spanning Tree (MST) of a network. Using this novel method can obtain the optimal or near-optimal solution for both CTPs and PRTPs.

Keywords: Classical transportation problem, Kruskal's algorithm, Minimum spanning tree, Optimal solution, Prohibited route transportation problem

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Introduction

Transporting products and services physically from several supply locations to various demand locations is a significant use of linear programming. The simplex approach may also be used to resolve a transportation problem that is formulated in terms of an LP model. It takes a long time to solve a transportation problem using simplex methods, even though it has many variables and restrictions. The MODI (Modified Distribution) Method and the Stepping Stone

Method are two transportation algorithms that have been created to address a transportation problem. There are several shipping routes from various supply locations to various demand locations that make up the basis of the transportation problem. The goal is to establish shipping routes between supply and demand centers to fulfill the demand for a certain amount of products or services at each destination center with the supply of those same goods or services at each supply center at the lowest possible transportation expense. The most straightforward transportation model was initially introduced by Hitchcock [1] in 1941, among many different kinds that exist today. Koopmans [2] in 1949 and Dantzig [3] in 1951 expanded on it. The development of several expansions to transportation models and methodologies has since taken place. TP has two solutions as Optimal Solution (OS) and Initial Feasible Solution (IFS). The MODI and the Stepping Stone Method are used to obtain OS and several heuristic techniques, including the least costly method (LCM) [4], the North-West Corner Method (NWCM) [4], and Vogel's approximation method (VAM) [4 – 6] are used to obtain IFS. Ashraful Babu [7], and Opara Jude [8] proposed new methods to find a feasible solution for TP. Selim Reza [9] developed a modified algorithm for LCM. E.M.U.S.B.Ekanayake [10 – 16] proposed several algorithms to solve TP in different ways. A method using standard deviations for solving unbalanced TP was proposed by T. Geetha [17]. Z.A.M.S. Juman [6, 18, 19] developed several approaches to address TPs. Moreover, many researchers such as Reena .G.Patel [20], Swati V. Kamble [21], M.M.Ahmed [22], Lakhveer Kaur [23], A.R.Khan [24], E.M.D.B.Ekanayake [13], Smita Sood [25], A. Edward Samuel [26], and D.A.S.Kadhem [27] introduced different types of technology to resolve transportation problems.

A special case of TP is the Prohibited or Unacceptable Route Transportation Problem (PRTP). It happens when one or more destinations are unable to receive shipments from one of the sources. When solving these kinds of minimization problems, we assume a very high unit cost (+M or $+\infty$) for a restricted cell and a very low profit (-M or $-\infty$) for a restricted cell. Then, proceed as usual. Few algorithms were developed to solve PRTP in literature. Joseph Ackora-Prah [28] proposed a method using a two-phase method and E.M.U.S.B.Ekanayake [12] proposed an algorithm using improved ant colony to solve PRTPs. Kruskal's algorithm is an algorithm, use to find the Minimum Spanning Tree (MST) of an undirected connected graph. Joseph Kruskal [29] published Kruskal's algorithm in 1956. This paper introduced an alternative algorithm to address both classical and prohibited route transportation problems based on Kruskal's algorithm. The structure of this paper is as follows: Basic definitions are provided in Section 2. Model representation is included in Section 3. In Sections 4 and 5, a novel algorithm is suggested, and it is illustrated using numerical examples. Section 6 provides a comparison of the proposed approach with the existing methods. The conclusion is included in the final section.

Preliminaries

Definition 1: (Sources and Destinations)

Sources (S_1, S_2, \dots, S_m) are the points in a TP from which commodities are distributed to the required points and demanding nodes (D_1, D_2, \dots, D_n) or the destination nodes in a TP are the locations where goods are supplied from sources.

Definition 2: (Supply Limit and Demand Requirement)

The quantity of a good needed to meet demand at each demand node is known as a source's supply limit and the term "demand requirement" refers to the amount of a commodity required to meet the demands of a demanding node.

Definition 3: (Balanced & Unbalanced Transportation Problem)

A TP is considered to be balanced if the total supply and demand are equal.

i.e. [Total Supply ($\sum_{i=1}^m a_i$) = Total Demand ($\sum_{j=1}^n b_j$)]

An unbalanced TP occurred when there is a difference between the total supply and demand.

i.e.[Total Supply ($\sum_{i=1}^m a_i$) \neq Total Demand ($\sum_{j=1}^n b_j$)]

Definition 4: (Minimum Spanning Tree (MST))

An undirected connected graph's subgraph known as a spanning tree. The spanning tree with the least total edge weight is the MST. The weight of a spanning tree is the total of the weights given to its edges.

Definition 5: (Kruskal's Algorithm)

Kruskal's Algorithm is a well-known greedy algorithm. Kruskal's approach can only be applied to weighted, connected, and undirected graphs. The phases of putting Kruskal's algorithm into practise are as follows:

- Step 1: Arrange all of the edges in ascending weight order.
- Step 2: Use the lowest weighted edge to join the points on the graph.
- Step 3: If adding an edge results in the creation of a cycle, remove it and go to the edge with the least amount of weight.
- Step 4: Add edges continuously until the MST is created and all of the vertices are connected.

Model Representation of The Transportation Problem

Take into account a situation where a certain item is normally created at m production facilities, known as sources, indicated by S_1, S_2, \dots, S_m with respective capacities of a_1, a_2, \dots, a_m and transported to n distribution centers, known as destinations, denoted by D_1, D_2, \dots, D_n with respective needs b_1, b_2, \dots, b_n .

Suppose that the amount transmitted and the transit cost from the i^{th} source to the j^{th} destination are, respectively, x_{ij} and c_{ij} . Where $i = 1, 2, \dots, m$ & $j = 1, 2, \dots, n$.

Mathematical Scenarios of TP:

Min $Z = \sum_{i=1}^m \sum_{j=1}^n x_{ij} c_{ij}$

Subject to:

$\sum_{j=1}^n x_{ij} = a_i$, $i = 1, 2, \dots, m$

$\sum_{i=1}^m x_{ij} = b_j$, $j = 1, 2, \dots, n$ $x_{ij} \geq 0$; $\forall i = 1, 2, \dots, m$ & $j = 1, 2, \dots, n$

Table 1: Display of the transportation problem in a table

Destination →	D_1	D_2	...	D_n	Supply (a_i)
Source ↓					
S_1	c_{11}	c_{12}	...	c_{1n}	a_1
S_2	c_{21}	c_{22}	...	c_{2n}	a_2
⋮	⋮	⋮	...	⋮	⋮
S_m	c_{m1}	c_{m2}	...	c_{mn}	a_m
Demand (b_j)	b_1	b_2	...	b_n	

Research Methodology

This section describes the proposed new algorithm. Both balanced, unbalanced classical and prohibited route transportation problems can solve using this proposed method. The optimal or near-optimal solution can be obtained using this technique. The following is a description of the steps in the suggested method:

Step 1: Check whether your TP is balanced or not. If it is not balanced introduce a new dummy row or column at the end of the source rows or destination columns.

Step 2: Construct the Transportation graphical representation.

Step 3: Find the Minimum Spanning Tree (MST) of the graphical network using Kruskal’s algorithm.

Step 4: Arrange the weight of MST in ascending order. If MST has an edge with zero weight, ignore that edge and go to the next edge in order.

Step 5: Assign the corresponding allocated value (x_{ij}) to cells as lined up.

Step 6: Adjust the supply and demand of the selected cell in TT and cross out the satisfied row or column.

Step 7: If the selected cell is already crossed out, then go to the next maximum value of the order.

Step 8: After assigning the every x_{ij} value to cells as lined up, if all the supplies and demands are not satisfied in TT, then assign the x_{ij} value to the cell which has minimum cost value (c_{ij}).

Step 9: After all, requirements are satisfied calculated the total transportation cost by the following equation:

$$i. e. \sum_{i=1}^m \sum_{j=1}^n x_{ij} c_{ij}$$

Here, c_{ij} = Unit transportation cost and x_{ij} = Corresponding allocated value.

Results and Discussion

In this part, the newly suggested approach will be used to analyze both balanced and unbalanced CTP as well as PRTP and will be compared to an optimal solution.

Example 1: BCTP_1 [10]

Step 1:

Table 2: Initial Balanced Classical Transportation Problem (BCTP_1)

	D ₁	D ₂	D ₃	D ₄	Supply
S ₁	50	60	100	50	20
S ₂	80	40	70	50	38
S ₃	90	70	30	50	16
Demand	10	18	22	24	

Step 2:

Fig. 1: Transportation Network of BCTP_1

Step 3:

Fig. 2: Minimum Spanning Tree of Transportation Network of BCTP_1

Step 4:

Allocation Order: $S_3D_3, S_2D_2, S_1D_1, S_1D_4, S_2D_4$

Steps 5 – 8:

Table 3: Allocation table of BCTP_1

	D ₁	D ₂	D ₃	D ₄	Supply
S ₁	50 (10)	60	100	50 (10)	20,10,0
S ₂	80	40 (18)	70 (6)	50 (14)	38,20,6,0
S ₃	90	70	30 (16)	50	16,0
Demand	10,0	18,0	22,6,0	24,14,0	

Step 9:

Total transportation cost = $(50 \times 10) + (50 \times 10) + (40 \times 18) + (70 \times 6) + (50 \times 14) + (30 \times 16) = 3320$

Optimal Solution = 3320

Example 2: UBCTP_1 [10]

Step 1:

Table 4: Initial Unbalanced Classical Transportation Problem (UCTP_1)

	D ₁	D ₂	D ₃	D ₄	Supply
S ₁	10	8	4	3	500
S ₂	12	14	20	2	400
S ₃	6	9	25	25	300
Demand	250	350	600	150	

Table 5: Balanced the UCTP_1 by adding a dummy source

	D ₁	D ₂	D ₃	D ₄	Supply
S ₁	10	8	4	3	500
S ₂	12	14	20	2	400
S ₃	6	9	25	25	300
D/S	0	0	0	0	150
Demand	250	350	600	150	

Fig. 3: Transportation Network of UCTP_1

Fig. 4: Minimum Spanning Tree of Transportation Network of UCTP_1

Step 4:

Allocation order: S₂D₄, S₁D₃, S₃D₁, S₃D₂

Steps 5 – 8:

Table 6: Allocation table of UCTP_1

	D ₁	D ₂	D ₃	D ₄	Supply
S ₁	10	8	4 (500)	3	500,0
S ₂	12	14 (250)	20	2 (150)	400,250,0
S ₃	6 (250)	9 (50)	25	25	300,50,0
D/S	0	0 (50)	0 (100)	0	150,50,0
Demand	250,0	350,300,250,0	600,100,0	150,0	

Step 9:

Total transportation cost = $(4 \times 500) + (14 \times 250) + (2 \times 150) + (6 \times 250) + (9 \times 50) = 7750$

Optimal Solution = 7750

Example 3: BPRTP_1 [12]

Step 1:

Table 7: Initial Balanced Prohibited Route Transportation Problem (BPRTP_1)

	D ₁	D ₂	D ₃	D ₄	D ₅	D ₆	Supply
S ₁	5	4	4	6	7	7	100
S ₂	8	6	6	5	7	7	200
S ₃	7	6	6	8	9	9	150
S ₄	M	M	0	0	M	0	110
Demand	80	40	50	60	80	250	

Step 2:

Fig. 5: Transportation Network of BPRTP_1

Step 3:

Fig. 6: Minimum Spanning Tree of Transportation Network of BPRTP_1

Step 4:

Allocation order: S₁D₂, S₁D₃, S₁D₁, S₂D₄

Steps 5 – 8:

Table 8: Allocation table of BPRTP_1

	D ₁	D ₂	D ₃	D ₄	D ₅	D ₆	Supply
S ₁	5 (10)	4 (40)	4 (50)	6	7	7	100, 60, 10, 0
S ₂	8	6	6	5 (60)	7 (80)	7 (60)	200, 120, 60, 0
S ₃	7 (70)	6	6	8	9	9 (80)	150, 80, 0
S ₄	M	M	0	0	M	0 (110)	110, 0
Demand	80, 70, 0	40, 0	50, 0	60, 0	80, 0	250, 140, 80, 0	

Step 9:

Total transportation cost = $(5 \times 10) + (4 \times 40) + (4 \times 50) + (5 \times 60) + (7 \times 80) + (7 \times 60) + (7 \times 70) + (9 \times 80) = 2900$

Optimal Solution = 2900

Example 4: UPRTP_1 [12]

Step 1:

Table 9: Initial Unbalanced Prohibited Route Transportation Problem (UPRTP_1)

	D ₁	D ₂	D ₃	D ₄	Supply
S ₁	14	15	16	17	40
S ₂	M	16	17	18	50
S ₃	M	M	15	16	30
S ₄	M	M	M	17	50
Demand	20	30	50	40	

Table 10: Balanced the UPRTP_1 by adding a dummy destination

	D ₁	D ₂	D ₃	D ₄	D/D	Supply
S ₁	14	15	16	17	0	40
S ₂	M	16	17	18	0	50
S ₃	M	M	15	16	0	30
S ₄	M	M	M	17	0	50
Demand	20	30	50	40	30	

Step 2:

Fig. 7: Transportation Network of UPRTP_1

Step 3:

Fig. 8: Minimum Spanning Tree of Transportation Network of UPRTP_1

Step 4:

Allocation order: S₁D₁, S₃D₃, S₁D₂, S₂D₂, S₄D₄

Steps 5 – 8:

Table 11: Allocation table of UPRTP_1

	D ₁	D ₂	D ₃	D ₄	D/D	Supply
S ₁	14 (20)	15 (20)	16	17	0	40,20,0
S ₂	M	16 (10)	17 (20)	18	0 (20)	50,40,20,0
S ₃	M	M	15 (30)	16	0	30,0
S ₄	M	M	M	17 (40)	0 (10)	50,10,0
Demand	20,0	30,10,0	50,20,0	40,0	30,20,0	

Step 9:

Total transportation cost = $(14 \times 20) + (15 \times 20) + (16 \times 10) + (17 \times 20) + (15 \times 30) + (17 \times 40) = 2210$

Optimal Solution = 2210

The two types of both balanced and unbalanced TPs are demonstrated in the examples above. CTP and PRTP, for instance. In every TP, the suggested approach provides an optimal solution, and when compared to the VAM method, it provides a better solution.

The Comparative Analysis of The Proposed Method

Balanced Classical Transportation Problems (BCTPs)

This study examines the results' comparisons to assess the suggested approach's efficacy. Table 12 shows the comparative analysis of Balanced Classical Transportation Problems (BCTP) with NWCM, LCM, VAM, and the proposed New Method (NEWM) for 10 instances.

Table 12: Comparative analysis of Balanced Classical Transportation Problems (BCTP)

Problem No. [10]	NWCM	LCM	VAM	NEWM	Optimal
BCTP_1	4160	3500	3320	3320	3320
BCTP_2	4400	2900	2850	2850	2850
BCTP_3	5925	4550	5125	4600	4525
BCTP_4	730	555	555	555	555
BCTP_5	520	475	475	475	435
BCTP_6	139	103	103	103	103
BCTP_7	226	156	156	156	156
BCTP_8	1500	1450	1500	1450	1390
BCTP_9	363	295	290	290	290
BCTP_10	234	191	187	187	183

Fig. 9 shows the outcomes of the bar graphs used to display the comparison results found in Table 12 in more detail.

Fig. 9: Comparative analysis of Balanced Classical Transportation Problems (BCTPs)

As can be seen from Table 12 above, the new approach is more effective than NWCM, LCM, and VAM in every situation where an increase in efficiency was achievable. Six out of ten instances give the optimal solution and other instances give the near-optimal solution. The numerical data of Table 12 represented in Appendix A.

Unbalanced Classical Transportation Problems (UCTPs)

Table 13 shows the comparative analysis of Unbalanced Classical Transportation Problems (UCTP) with NWCM, LCM, VAM, and NEWM for 10 instances and Figure 10 shows its graphical representation.

Table 13: Comparative analysis of Unbalanced Classical Transportation Problems (UCTP)

Problem No. [9, 10 14, 17]	NWCM	LCM	VAM	NEWM	Optimal
UCTP_1	18800	7750	8350	7750	7750
UCTP_2	1815	1695	1745	1695	1650
UCTP_3	12825	10375	11125	10375	10375
UCTP_4	13100	9200	9200	9200	9200
UCTP_5	1125	965	965	965	960
UCTP_6	8150	5750	6000	5750	5600
UCTP_7	5070	4900	5020	4900	4720
UCTP_8	1780	1465	1555	1465	1465
UCTP_9	1010	840	880	840	840
UCTP_10	788	606	630	606	606

Fig. 10 shows the outcomes of the bar graphs used to display the comparison results found in Table 13 in more detail.

Fig. 10: Comparative analysis of Unbalanced Classical Transportation Problems (UCTPs)

The new strategy outperforms NWCM, LCM, and VAM in every circumstance where a gain in efficiency was possible, as shown in Table 13 and Figure 10 above. The optimal answer is provided in six out of ten cases, and other cases provide a nearly optimal solution. The numerical data of Table 13 represented in Appendix B.

Prohibited Route Transportation Problems (PRTPs)

Table 14 shows the comparative analysis of both Balanced Prohibited Route Transportation Problems (BPRTP) and Unbalanced Prohibited Route Transportation Problems (UPRTP) for five instances.

Table 14: Comparative analysis of both balanced and unbalanced Prohibited Route Transportation Problems (PRTP)

Problem No. [12], [28]	NWCM	LCM	VAM	NEWM	Optimal
BPRTP_1	80012120	10260	2900	2900	2900
UPRTP_1	2230	2210	2230	2210	2210
UPRTP_2	39300	36100	36800	36800	36100
UPRTP_3	10400	9100	9100	9100	9100
UPRTP_4	11635	11565	11565	11565	11565

Fig. 11 shows the outcomes of the bar graphs used to display the comparison results found in Table 14 in more detail. The numerical data of Table 14 represented in Appendix C.

Fig. 11: Comparative analysis of both balanced and unbalanced Prohibited Route Transportation Problems (PRTPs)

According to the data above (Table 14, Fig. 11), the new approach is superior to the current methods. In four of the five cases, it delivers the best outcomes, while the other result is nearly as good as the VAM approach. Table 15 displays the comparison of randomly generated 10 instances of both CTPs and PRTPs.

Randomly Generated Transportation Problems

Table 15: Comparative analysis of randomly generated both classical and prohibited route transportation problems

Problem No.	NWCM	LCM	VAM	NEWM	Optimal
CTP_1	4125	3500	3500	3500	3500
CTP_2	9050	9275	9275	9275	8400
CTP_3	4150	3850	2900	2850	2850
CTP_4	15925	13150	12825	10650	10650
CTP_5	30700	14700	20400	14700	14700

PRTP_1	11665	11665	11665	11665	11665
PRTP_2	40550	31300	32150	31300	30650
PRTP_3	1215	1215	1215	1215	1215
PRTP_4	8050	6400	6400	6400	6400
PRTP_5	23400	23250	23250	23250	23250

Fig. 12 shows the comparison data from Table 15 as well as the bar graphs that were used to display them.

Fig. 12: Comparative analysis of randomly generated both classical and prohibited route transportation problems

The suggested approach (NEWA) is eight out of ten times more effective than NWCM, LCM, and VAM, as is seen in Table 15 and Fig. 12. The other two situations provide close to optimal answers, but those are better than VAM solutions. The numerical data of Table 15 represented in Appendix D.

Conclusion

A novel algorithm for obtaining a near-to-optimal solution to the TP was put forth in the present study. For resolving the transportation issue, many methods have been suggested in the literature. Some techniques focused on identifying an initial basic feasible solution, while others sought the best optimal answer. However, this study proposed a new algorithm to solve both classical and prohibited route transportation problems using Kruskal’s algorithm. Kruskal’s algorithm is used to find the minimum spanning tree of an undirected graph. This proposed algorithm can apply both balanced and unbalanced transportation problems. The method is also simple to comprehend and provides us with optimal or nearly optimal solutions after a few repetitions.

This method was used in this study to address 35 problems. 25 of them are chosen from the literature, while the other 10 are generated at random. Those 35 problems were analyzed comparatively with other existing methods. Consequently, demonstrate that the novel method is effective in terms of the quality of the solution when compared to the ways this research evaluated.

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Appendix A

Problem No. [10]	Data
BCTP_1	$c_{ij} = \{50, 60, 100, 50; 80, 40, 70, 50; 90, 70, 30, 50\}$ $S_{ij} = \{20, 38, 16\}, D_{ij} = \{10, 18, 22, 24\}$
BCTP_2	$c_{ij} = \{3, 1, 7, 4; 2, 6, 5, 9; 8, 3, 3, 2\}$ $S_{ij} = \{300, 400, 500\}, D_{ij} = \{250, 350, 400, 200\}$
BCTP_3	$c_{ij} = \{6, 8, 10; 7, 11, 11; 4, 5, 12\}$ $S_{ij} = \{150, 175, 275\}, D_{ij} = \{200, 100, 300\}$
BCTP_4	$c_{ij} = \{6, 4, 1; 3, 8, 7; 4, 4, 2\}$ $S_{ij} = \{50, 40, 60\}, D_{ij} = \{20, 95, 35\}$
BCTP_5	$c_{ij} = \{10, 2, 20, 11; 12, 7, 9, 20; 4, 14, 16, 18\}$ $S_{ij} = \{15, 25, 10\}, D_{ij} = \{5, 15, 15, 15\}$
BCTP_6	$c_{ij} = \{9, 12, 9, 6, 9, 10; 7, 3, 7, 7, 5, 5; 6, 5, 9, 11, 3, 1; 6, 8, 11, 2, 2, 10\}$ $S_{ij} = \{5, 6, 2, 9\}, D_{ij} = \{4, 4, 6, 2, 4, 2\}$
BCTP_7	$c_{ij} = \{4, 6, 9, 5; 2, 6, 4, 1; 5, 7, 2, 9\}$

	$S_{ij} = \{16, 12, 15\}, D_{ij} = \{12, 14, 9, 8\}$
BCTP_8	$c_{ij} = \{4, 3, 5; 6, 5, 4; 8, 10, 7\}$ $S_{ij} = \{90, 80, 100\}, D_{ij} = \{70, 120, 80\}$
BCTP_9	$c_{ij} = \{4, 1, 2, 4, 4; 2, 3, 2, 2, 3; 3, 5, 2, 4, 4\}$ $S_{ij} = \{60, 35, 40\}, D_{ij} = \{22, 45, 20, 18, 30\}$
BCTP_10	$c_{ij} = \{5, 7, 10, 5, 3; 8, 6, 9, 12, 14; 10, 9, 8, 10, 15\}$ $S_{ij} = \{5, 10, 10\}, D_{ij} = \{3, 3, 10, 5, 4\}$

Appendix B

Problem No. [9, 10, 14, 17]	Data
UCTP_1	$c_{ij} = \{10, 8, 4, 3; 12, 14, 20, 2; 6, 9, 25, 25\}$ $S_{ij} = \{500, 400, 300\}, D_{ij} = \{250, 350, 600, 150\}$
UCTP_2	$c_{ij} = \{6, 10, 14; 12, 19, 21; 15, 14, 17\}$ $S_{ij} = \{50, 50, 50\}, D_{ij} = \{30, 40, 55, 25\}$
UCTP_3	$c_{ij} = \{12, 10, 6, 13; 19, 8, 16, 25; 17, 15, 15, 20; 23, 22, 26, 12\}$ $S_{ij} = \{150, 500, 600, 225\}, D_{ij} = \{300, 500, 75, 100\}$
UCTP_4	$c_{ij} = \{5, 8, 6, 6, 3; 4, 7, 7, 6, 5; 8, 4, 6, 6, 4\}$ $S_{ij} = \{800, 500, 900\}, D_{ij} = \{400, 400, 500, 400, 800\}$
UCTP_5	$c_{ij} = \{6, 1, 9, 3; 11, 5, 2, 8; 10, 12, 4, 7\}$ $S_{ij} = \{70, 55, 70\}, D_{ij} = \{85, 35, 50, 45\}$
UCTP_6	$c_{ij} = \{5, 4, 8, 6, 5; 4, 5, 4, 3, 2; 3, 6, 5, 8, 4\}$ $S_{ij} = \{600, 400, 1000\}, D_{ij} = \{450, 400, 200, 250, 300\}$
UCTP_7	$c_{ij} = \{10, 15, 12, 12; 8, 10, 11, 9; 11, 12, 13, 10\}$ $S_{ij} = \{200, 150, 120\}, D_{ij} = \{140, 120, 80, 220\}$
UCTP_8	$c_{ij} = \{5, 6, 9; 3, 5, 10; 6, 7, 6; 6, 4, 10\}$ $S_{ij} = \{100, 75, 50, 75\}, D_{ij} = \{70, 80, 120\}$
UCTP_9	$c_{ij} = \{3, 4, 6; 7, 3, 8; 6, 4, 5; 7, 5, 2\}$ $S_{ij} = \{100, 80, 90, 120\}, D_{ij} = \{110, 110, 60\}$
UCTP_10	$c_{ij} = \{7, 8, 11, 10; 10, 12, 5, 4; 6, 11, 10, 9\}$ $S_{ij} = \{30, 45, 35\}, D_{ij} = \{20, 28, 19, 33\}$

Appendix C

Problem No. [12], [28]	Data
BPRTP_1	$c_{ij} = \{5, 4, 4, 6, 7, 7; 8, 6, 6, 5, 7, 7; 7, 6, 6, 8, 9, 9; M, M, 0, 0, M, 0\}$ $S_{ij} = \{100, 200, 150, 110\},$ $D_{ij} = \{80, 40, 50, 60, 80, 250\}$
UPRTP_1	$c_{ij} = \{14, 15, 16, 17; M, 16, 17, 18; M, M, 15, 16; M, M, M, 17\}$ $S_{ij} = \{40, 50, 30, 50\}, D_{ij} = \{20, 30, 50, 40\}$
UPRTP_2	$c_{ij} = \{10, 13, 16, 19; M, 10, 13, 16;$ $M, 15, 18, 21; M, M, 15, 18; M, M, 20, 23; M, M, M, 15\}$ $S_{ij} = \{700, 700, 200, 700, 200, 700\},$

	$D_{ij} = \{300, 700, 900, 800\}$
UPRTP_3	$c_{ij} = \{10, 11, 12; 15, 16, 17;$ $M, 10, 11; M, 15, 16; M, M, 10; M, M, 15\}$ $S_{ij} = \{300, 100, 300, 100, 300, 100\},$ $D_{ij} = \{200, 400, 300\}$
UPRTP_4	$c_{ij} = \{5.0, 5.5; 6.25, 6.75; M, 5.0; M, 6.25\}$ $S_{ij} = \{920, 250, 920, 250\}, D_{ij} = \{800, 1400\}$

Appendix D

Problem No.	Data
CTP_1	$c_{ij} = \{19, 16, 17; 13, 13, 9; 7, 17, 19\}$ $S_{ij} = \{100, 50, 100\}, D_{ij} = \{25, 175, 50\}$
CTP_2	$c_{ij} = \{13, 15, 11, 17; 9, 21, 22, 10; 5, 26, 21, 10\}$ $S_{ij} = \{50, 300, 250\}, D_{ij} = \{25, 175, 100, 300\}$
CTP_3	$c_{ij} = \{4, 2, 4, 1; 3, 10, 5, 1; 4, 8, 8, 6; 4, 10, 2, 7\}$ $S_{ij} = \{400, 300, 250, 50\}, D_{ij} = \{100, 300, 250, 350\}$
CTP_4	$c_{ij} = \{37, 30, 19; 38, 87, 51; 38, 74, 78\}$ $S_{ij} = \{25, 125, 100\}, D_{ij} = \{100, 50, 150\}$
CTP_5	$c_{ij} = \{2, 86, 66; 31, 29, 75; 43, 23, 48; 3, 100, 31\}$ $S_{ij} = \{700, 100, 200, 200\}, D_{ij} = \{500, 300, 200\}$
PRTP_1	$c_{ij} = \{12, 59, 65; 68, 3, 82; M, 88, 80\}$ $S_{ij} = \{100, 150, 50\}, D_{ij} = \{150, 65, 85\}$
PRTP_2	$c_{ij} = \{30, 53, 29; M, 80, 84; 20, M, 71; 25, 35, 40\}$ $S_{ij} = \{400, 150, 50, 200\}, D_{ij} = \{200, 250, 350\}$
PRTP_3	$c_{ij} = \{8, 10, 11, 18; M, 7, 9, 17; M, M, 12, 19; M, M, M, 12\}$ $S_{ij} = \{15, 15, 60, 10\}, D_{ij} = \{10, 20, 40, 30\}$
PRTP_4	$c_{ij} = \{20, 25, 40; 90, 75, 50; M, 30, 35; M, M, 40\}$ $S_{ij} = \{30, 70, 60, 40\}, D_{ij} = \{60, 40, 50\}$
PRTP_5	$c_{ij} = \{99, 96, M; 52, M, 58; M, 53, 80\}$ $S_{ij} = \{50, 100, 250\}, D_{ij} = \{150, 375, 25\}$

